

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Physiology and plant nutrition

***Sesbania rostrata* and *Aeschynomene afra* effects on crop establishment of transplanted lowland rice**

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Anaerobic decomposition products in flooded soils may affect root and shoot growth of newly transplanted rice seedlings after organic matter amendment. We evaluated the effects of *S. rostrata* and *A. afra* green manure (GM) amendment on crop establishment of transplanted lowland rice by conducting a field experiment at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center (MRRTC), Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, during the 1988 dry season.

The soil is a Vertic Tropaquept with pH 5.9. Each kilogram of soil contains 14 g organic C, 1.1 g total N, CEC 38 cmol_c, 450 g clay, and 50 g sand. The field was irrigated and kept flooded for 2 wk before wetland preparation to allow the soil redox potential to reach equilibrium. The field was plowed once (15- to 20-cm depth) and harrowed twice. We broadcast and incorporated single superphosphate, KCl, and zinc sulfate heptahydrate at 26-50-4.5 kg P-K-Zn/ha before transplanting rice.

GM plants grown for 45 d outside the trial area were harvested, transferred to the experimental field, chopped into 5-cm-long pieces, and incorporated by hand into moist soil after the flooded plots were drained 1 d before transplanting. GM was basally incorporated at 90 kg N/ha using 2.9 t dry matter/ha for *S. rostrata* (3.2% N, C/N = 12) and 2.43 t/ha for *A. afra* (3.7% N, C/N = 12). We compared these GM treatments with urea N application at the same rate and with a zero fertilizer N control.

The experimental design was a randomized complete block with four replications.

Crop growth rates and N uptake rates of transplanted IR64 rice as affected by *Sesbania rostrata* and *Aeschynomene afra* GM or urea application. MRRTC. Muñoz. Nueva Ecija, Philippines. 1988 dry season.

N source ^a	Crop growth rates (g/m ² per d)		N uptake rates (mg/m ² per d)	
	5-13 DT	13-20 DT	5-13 DT	13-20 DT
<i>S. rostrata</i>	0.8	2.3	25	112
<i>A. afra</i>	0.7	2.1	24	110
Urea	1.4	7.0	51	245
No fertilizer N	1.9	3.9	61	145
LSD (0.05)	0.3	1.2	9	21

^a N rate: 90 kg/ha as GM basally applied, or as urea applied in 2/3-1/3 split.

Twenty-one-day-old IR64 rice seedlings were transplanted into water-saturated soil at 3-4 plants/hill at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Plots were 29.4 m². Floodwater depth was kept at 5 cm after transplanting.

Six rice hills were sampled at 5 d after transplanting (DT) and weekly thereafter until panicle initiation (PI) to determine dry weight, N content, and N uptake. After PI, four hills were sampled biweekly until crop maturity.

Yellowing of plants and rice seedling death were observed in the first 7 DT. Missing hills were replaced. Plant damage may have been due partly to transplanting shock, but symptoms were more severe in GM treatments.

Crop growth rates and N uptake rates were significantly lower ($P = 0.05$) in GM treatments than in urea and control treatments (see table). *A. afra* seemed to damage rice seedlings more than *S. rostrata* did, but this was not significantly reflected in their crop growth rates.

Exchangeable NH₄⁺-N levels at the

MRRTC site were high enough (data not presented) to provide N for the rice seedlings as proven by the higher crop growth rate with zero fertilizer N than with GM. Therefore, other factors must have affected seedling vigor.

High concentrations of soil CO₂ due to GM decomposition and the release of organic acids, phenolic substances, and other organic compounds probably affected seedling root and shoot growth. However, rice plants overcame the additional stress caused by GM amendment and gave the same N uptake at 34 DT and dry matter at 41 DT as did plants fertilized with urea (data not presented).

In this experiment where missing rice hills were replaced, grain yields in urea and GM treatments did not significantly differ (data not presented). But in farmers' fields, where dead rice hills are not replanted, farmers should delay transplanting by a few days after GM incorporation to avoid problems in establishing the crop. □

Response to different Zn carriers of rice grown on Ustifluvents in India

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We studied the relative efficiency of Zn carriers applied as foliar sprays for rice on Ustifluvents. Soil was sandy loam with pH 8.4, EC 0.30 dS/m, 0.45% organic C, and 0.45 mg DTPA extractable Zn/kg soil.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. Urea, diammonium phosphate, and muriate of potash were applied at 120 kg N, 27 kg P, and 24 kg K/ha.

We transplanted 45-d-old seedlings of long-duration, short-statured rice variety Jaya and applied three types of Zn in foliar sprays at two concentrations each (see table). Plants were sprayed 4 wk after transplanting and twice more at a 10-d interval. The crop was grown to maturity and the yield